

Web Content Analysis Of Barti & Yashada Training Institute Libraries: A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

This research represented that web content analysis of BARTI and YASHADA training institute libraries. Online survey method is used and design 51 check-lists for data collection. In this research positive and negative points are systematically analysed. All data is represented in percentile form and give some essential suggestions.

Keywords: Web Content, Content Analysis, BARTI, YASHADA, Library Websites.

Introduction:

Each and every institutional organization develops their website. Now a day, all information easily available on websites. It is the mirror of institution. Web 2.0 is best platform for internet. All changes and development of internet is possible with help of web 2.0. In this research two institutional library websites are trying to systematically analyses. Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Research and Training Institution (BARTI) and Yashwantrao Chavan Academy of Development Administration (YASHADA) are well reputed institutions in Maharashtra. These two institutions library websites are systematically analysed with the help of 51 check-lists.

Web 2.0:

Web 2.0 is the greatest platform for inter user face. This term was coined by Darcy DiNucci in 1999 and this term was popular by Tim O'Reilly. The first conference on web 2.0 is best platform to interact users and internet. With the help of web 2.0 users are display some kind of information, use social media, sharing videos, massages, social activities, etc. Web 2.0 is useful in every field and library is not different from these. Library is developed their own website and provide e-books, e-journals, OPAC, e-database, etc. Web 2.0 is useful to develop digital library and digitisation.

Library 2.0:

If web 2.0 was open platform for users then library 2.0 is not to back foot for provide services to their users. With the help of web 2.0 library websites are provided e-books, e-journals & e-databases links to their users. To create digital library is also possible and all data is available on websites in digital form. Library 2.0 is played vital role to fulfil the need of library users and their demands.

Scope and limitation of the study:

Present study has covered Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Research and Training Institute (BARTI) and Yashwantrao Chavan Academy of Development Administration (YASHADA). These two institutions are situated in Maharashtra state. In this research analysed only websites with the help of checklist. This study is limited to only two websites.

Objectives of research paper:

- To know how to develop website.
- To examine the content of library websites.
- To know resource information available on websites.
- To suggest some points for improve website.

Review of Related Literature:

Gautam, Virendra Kumar (2017):

Present study deals with content analysis of websites of central university libraries in Delhi. As per the record of University Grants Commission website, there are five central universities in Delhi. These are Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU), Jamia Millia Islamic University (JMIU), Jawahar Lal Nehru University (JNU), South Asian University (SAU) and University of Delhi. This study adopted online survey method. Data was collected from Central University library websites with the help of check-list. Most of library provided (100%) of general information about library. (100%) of library websites are displayed information about books, e-books, journals, e-journals. Most of library websites provided bi-lingual, digital archives, multi media collection, etc. All library websites are well develop and maintained.

Chikkamanju (2017):

Present study was investigated that website analysis of University of Agricultural sciences library in Karnataka state. According to Radhakrishnan Commission report in 1949, 'Library is the heart of any University'. Present study is limited to only four university of Agriculture science library websites in Karnataka i.e. UASD, UASB, UASR and UASS. Researcher has adopted survey method for present study and designed check-list for data collection. Most of library websites are not updated frequently and also UASR library have not given link to in their library website. Other three library websites are properly provided information such as library collection, new arrivals, OPAC, digital library, reading room, etc.

Ambik, C. A. & Ganesan, P (2021):

This study was investigated that central University library websites in India. Total 49 central universities are situated in India but only 13 central University libraries are selected which established in 2001 to 2010. For this study researcher was adopted online survey method and choose checklist for data collection. Most of central library websites have not displayed information on mission, copyright, sitemap and library committee. It was found that maximum central University library websites have displayed information about books and journals. Only five library websites have provided information about news papers. All central library websites have well developed and maintained.

Sonule, Rahul C. (2021):

Present study was represented that web content analysis of C.P.E. college library websites of Marathwada region. According to University Grants Commission in Marathwada region situated 10 C.P.E. colleges. This study is concerned to only eight

C.P.E. colleges and other two library websites are under construction. Researcher has used survey method and designed check-list for data collection. Total 61 items are included in check-list. Most of library websites have displayed general library information. Only 25% library websites are used animation in their design. 62.5% library websites are provided web OPAC service. All library websites are open in Google and Yahoo search engines. After analyses the data all library websites are well and good developed.

Arandhara, Ramyajyoti (2021):

Present study was indicated that content analysis of library websites of four selected universities in Assam. And present research analysed four selected universities are Krishna Kanta Handiqui library of Gauhati University, Central library of Tezpur University, Lakshminath Bezbaroa library of Dibrugarh University and Dr. Suryya Kumar Bhuyan library of cotton University. This research adopted online survey method and chosen check-list for data collection. All library websites are user friendly and attractive. In the digital age all library websites are provided information i.e. instant messaging, RSS feeds, digital reference services and FAQs, etc.

Methodology:

This study discusses about BARTI & YASHADA library websites in Maharashtra state. All websites are systematically analysed by using checklist. In this research checklist is prepared for data collection. Total 51 items are included in checklist. Collected data is represented very carefully in percentile form.

Data analysis:

Checklist is used for collection of data. Researcher has tried to represent the data in different level to understand easily by everyone.

Table no. 1

List of sample population

Sr. No.	Name of University	Web Address
01	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Training Institute (BARTI)	www.barti.org
02	(YASHADA)	www.yashada.in

Data was collected during August 17, 2022 to August 20, 2022 library websites.

Table No. 2

General Library Information

Sr. No.	Aspects	Yes	No	Percentage of Yes
01	About Statement	2	0	100
02	Working Hours	1	1	50

03	Membership Information	1	1	50
04	Library Rules	1	1	50
05	Library Sections	1	1	50
06	Facilities/Services	1	1	50

Table no. 2 shows that (100%) of library websites are displayed 'about statement' and (50%) of library websites are provided

information about, 'working hours', 'membership information', 'library rules', 'library sections', 'facilities and services'.

Table No. 3
Authority

Sr. No.	Aspects	Yes	No	Percentage of Yes
01	Website Updating Date	1	1	50
02	Maintained Without Any Internal/External Advertisement	2	0	100
03	Links to Mobile Site	0	2	00
04	Page Under Construction	1	1	50
05	Page Title Shows in Top Side	2	0	100
06	Dead Link	0	2	00
07	Availability of Home Link in Every Page	2	0	100
08	Website Index	1	1	50
09	Site is Larger (more than 4 pages)	2	0	100
10	Multilingual Information	0	2	00

Above Table shows that (100%) of the library websites has indicated 'Maintained Without Any Internal/External Advertisement', 'Page Title Appears in the Top', 'Home Link in Every Page', 'Site is Larger (more than 4 pages)'. (50%) of library

websites have provided, 'website updating date', 'page under construction', 'website index'. (0%) library websites have not provided information about, 'link to mobile site', 'are there dead link' and 'multilingual information'.

Table No. 4
Information Resources

Sr. No.	Type	Yes	No	Percentage of Yes
01	Books	0	2	00
02	Print Journals	0	2	00
03	Electronic Journals	1	1	50
04	Book Bank	0	2	00
05	Back Volumes of Journals	0	2	00
06	Non-Print Media	0	2	00
07	Full Text e-journals	1	1	50
08	Bibliographic Database	0	2	00
09	Open Access Journals	2	0	100
10	Links to e-books	0	2	00
11	Licensing Information	2	0	100
12	Copyright Issue	2	0	100

Table no. 4 reveals that library resources information, (100%) of information displayed OPAC, licence information, copyright issue. (50%) of information displayed e-journals, full text e-journals. No one can display

information about, books, print journals, book bank, back volumes of journals, non-print media, bibliographic database and link toe-books.

Table No. 5
C.A.S.

Sr. No.	Type	Yes	No	Percentage of Yes
01	New Arrivals	1	1	50
02	News Alert	1	1	50
03	RSS Feed	1	1	50
04	Link to SNS	0	2	00

Table no. 5 shows that, about current awareness services, (50%) of library websites have, 'new arrivals', 'news alert', 'RSS feed'.

Library website has not provided 'link to SNS'.

Table No. 6
Website Classification by Design Matter

Sr. No.	Design	Yes	No	Percentage of Yes
01	Graphics	2	0	100
02	Animations	1	1	50
03	Site Map	1	1	50
04	BG & Font Colour Combination	2	0	100
05	Download Option	2	0	100
06	Hit Counter	1	1	50
07	Photo Gallery	1	1	50
08	Text-only Version	0	2	00
09	Site Designer	2	0	100

It is observed from the above Table no.6 that (100%) of library websites have provided 'Graphic in Site', 'BG & Font Colour Combination', 'Download Option', 'Site Designer'. (50%) of library websites have

displayed, 'animation', 'Site Map', 'hit counter', 'photo gallery'. (0%) of library websites have 'Text-only Version' and 'site designer'.

Table No. 7
Criteria of Search

Sr. No.	Aspects	Yes	No	Percentage of Yes
01	Facility of Search	0	2	00
02	Links to External Search Engine	0	2	00
03	No. of external Links (More than 5)	2	0	100
04	Web OPAC	1	1	50
05	A-Z Title List	0	2	00
06	Publisher Wise List	0	2	00
07	Subject Wise List	0	2	00

Table no. 7 shows that (100%) of library websites has provided 'No. of external Links (More than 5)'. (50%) 'Web OPAC'. No one

can provide, 'search facility', 'Links to External Search Engine', 'A-Z Title List', 'Publisher Wise List', 'Subject Wise List'.

Table No. 8
Search Engine Retrieval Ranking

Sr. No.	Rank	Yes	No	Percentage of Yes
01	1 st Rank on Google Search	2	0	100
02	1 st Rank on Yahoo Search	2	0	100

Above table reveals that all websites in Google and Yahoo search engines provide 1st rank with key word search.

Table No. 9
Website Domain Type

Sr. No.	Particulars	.org	.in
01	Number	1	1
02	Percentage	50	50

It is observed from above table, (50%) of websites have domain type 'org' and 'in'.

Conclusion:

The present study is based on 51 items checklists responses. It shows both positive and negative facts about the content of the BARTI and YASHADA library websites. Most of the library websites are weak in web-

based services. On the basis of the findings of the study, following suggestions will be useful for improvement in the universities library websites.

Suggestions:

1. Library websites should provide date of updating.

2. Library websites should display website index.
3. Multilingual information should be provided on library websites.
4. The websites should provide bibliographic database.
5. Library websites should provide RSS feed.
6. Link of social networking site should be provided.
7. Library websites should provide links to external search engines.

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